

European Researchers' Night 2024/25

D5.1 Management Report 2024

Project information

Project name	EU-EMBRACES
Full project name	Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools
Grant number	101162414
Project coordinator	ITQB NOVA
Project duration	20 months

Document information

Deliverable name and number	D5.1 Management Report 2024		
Due date	M9		
Actual submission date	January 2025		
Contributing partners	Eleonora Tulumello (ITQB NOVA), Ana Sanchez (ITQB NOVA)		
Deliverable type	R	Document, report	X
	DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	
	DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos etc.	
	DMP	Data Management Plan	
Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Version history

Version	Date	Comments
1.0	31/01/2025	

Table of Contents

1. | Executive Summary

2. | Project and consortium overview

3. | Overview of the work carried out (Months 1-9)

3.1. Work Packages Updates

Work Package 1 (WP1): Awareness Campaign 1

Progress report by task

Work Package 2 (WP2): Activities during the Night 1

Progress report by task

Work Package 3 (WP3): Researchers at Schools activities 1

Progress report by task

Work Package 4 (WP4): Impact assessment 1

Progress report by task

Work Package 5 (WP5): Management 1

Progress report by task

3.2. Deviations from the plan, challenges and mitigation measures

WP1: Awareness Campaign 1

WP2: Activities during the Night 1

WP4: Impact assessment 1

WP5: Management 1

4. | Current impact overview

5. | Plans for upcoming months (10-20)

5.1 | Risk Management for upcoming months

6. | Conclusion

1. | Executive Summary

This document provides an overview of the project management efforts implemented within the period M1-M9 of the project **EU-EMBRACES (Empowering Minds: Boosting Research in Citizen Engagement and Schools)** to ensure effective coordination and execution of the project. It describes the roles and responsibilities of the consortium partners, including the coordinator, as well as the tasks and activities they have undertaken throughout the reporting period.

The report includes a detailed account of the work carried out within each work package, highlighting any deviations from the initial plans and the mitigation measures adopted. In addition, it outlines the management strategies and plans to address upcoming challenges in the next phases of the project. This summary aims to provide a comprehensive perspective on the project's progress while ensuring transparency and alignment with its goals.

2. | Project and consortium overview

The EU-EMBRACES is a Horizon Project designed to foster engagement and inclusivity in Science Communication, addressing socio-economic disparities in access to science and innovation. The project seeks to actively involve underrepresented communities, particularly those from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds, demonstrating how Horizon Europe Missions can positively impact their lives.

Spanning 20 months over the biennium 2024-2025, EU-EMBRACES aims to host two editions of the European Researchers' Night and deliver over 250 activities across 9 venues in Portugal. The initiative brings together researchers, schools, local authorities, NGOs, and companies to promote societal engagement and stimulate innovation-driven growth.

The project is divided into two phases—May 2024 to April 2025, and May 2025 to December 2025—and comprises ten Work Packages (WPs), with five assigned to each phase. These correspond to the project's main activities:

- Awareness campaigns (WP1 and WP6)
- Activities during the main events (European Researchers Nights 2024 and 2025) and build-up events (WP2 and WP7)
- Researchers at Schools activities (WP3 and WP8)

- Impact Assessment (WP4 and WP9)
- Management of the project (WP5 and WP10)

The consortium of the EU-EMBRACES project consists of three main partners:

- **Ciência Viva – Agência Nacional para a Cultura Científica e Tecnológica**, the national agency for Scientific Culture and Technology;
- **i3S – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde**, a research center with robust educational programs;
- **ITQB NOVA – Instituto de Tecnologia Química e Biológica António Xavier**, a research and academic institution with extensive outreach experience;

The project is coordinated by **ITQB NOVA**, which is responsible for WP5 and WP10 (Management 1/2) and oversees the administrative, legal, accounting, and financial management, while supporting the partners. ITQB NOVA has set up common methodologies and procedures for the consortium, monitors the project's progress, and ensures adherence to schedules and guidelines. Additionally, ITQB NOVA coordinates with EU services, managing and reporting on the project's progress.

ITQB NOVA is also in charge of the WP4 and WP9 (Impact Assessment 1/2) and organized the main event *European Researchers' Night (ERN)* for the 2024 edition at Marina de Oeiras.

i3S is responsible for the WP1 and WP6 (Awareness Campaign 1/2), which involve the awareness campaign, the development of the project's image, the communication plan, and national dissemination.

i3S also organized the main event *ERN* for the 2024 edition at i3S Institute, in Asprela.

Ciência Viva is responsible for WP2 and WP7 (Activities during the Night 1/2), managing the Activities during the Night and the Build-up events for 2024 and 2025 editions, and for the WP3 and WP8 (Researchers at Schools activities 1/2), coordinating the activities aimed at engaging schools and underserved neighborhoods.

Additionally, **Ciência Viva** ensures close cooperation with seven **Ciência Viva Science Centres**, which are key **associated partners** for the overall success of the project: **Centro Ciência Viva de Braga, Centro Ciência Viva de Bragança, Centro Ciência Viva de Vila Nova de Foz Côa, Centro Ciência Viva de Alviela, Centro Ciência Viva de Estremoz, Centro Ciência Viva de Lagos**.

Ciência Viva organized the main event *ERN* for the 2024 edition at Pavilhão do Conhecimento in Lisbon, whereas each of the seven **Ciência Viva Science Centres** organized the main event *ERN* at their respective venues.

Finally, all partners and associated partners are responsible for organizing and implementing the activities related to WP3 and WP8 (Researchers at Schools activities 1/2).

3. | Overview of the work carried out (Months 1-9)

The tasks and activities of the EU-EMBRACES project are divided into ten work packages. The first five are scheduled for the initial phase of the project (M1-M12, May 2024 to April 2025), while the remaining five are planned for the second phase (M13-M20, May 2025 to December 2025).

3.1. Work Packages Updates

Below is a list of the WPs and the work carried out so far in each of them.

Work Package 1 (WP1): Awareness Campaign 1

WP1 focused on the communication and promotion of the European Researchers' Night (ERN) as a year-round concept, emphasizing science outreach through build-up events, "Researchers at Schools" and other activities. Special efforts were made to use online platforms to build connections with younger generations. The WP aimed to maximise public participation, establish ERN as a recognizable brand, and highlight EU-funded research.

Progress report by task

Task 1.1. - Integrated Communication Plan and Web Tools:

A strategic communication plan was developed, along with brand identity guidelines and a media kit (logos, social media copy, press releases).

Social media accounts (Facebook, X, Instagram, YouTube, and TikTok) were either created or reactivated and managed to disseminate information effectively.

Task 1.2 - Online Platforms and Build-Up Activities:

A website with interactive features, including maps, booking systems, and a volunteer scientist pool, was developed and launched. While i3S managed the website's content, the consortium partners decided to host the site on Ciência Viva's server. This decision was based on Ciência Viva's expertise in managing multiple websites and their dedicated IT team, which could efficiently handle increasing demands.

Throughout the year, science communication activities, such as build-up events and 'Researchers at Schools' programs, were implemented to build momentum in preparation for the NIGHT.

Task 1.3 – Ongoing Communication:

Engaging content was created and shared on social media and websites to maintain public interest and visibility leading up to and following the NIGHT.

Updates, coverage of activities, and post-event communications were provided to sustain engagement and lay the groundwork for future editions.

1. Publicity and Media:

TV and newspaper advertising campaigns were launched.

EU support for science was highlighted through "EU Corners" at main events, which showcased EU-funded research projects and Missions.

Detailed description of the work carried out and its impact was reported in the deliverables D1.1 – Integrated Communication plan and D1.2 – Awareness campaign, delivered respectively in July and November.

Work Package 2 (WP2): Activities during the Night 1

WP2 focuses on organizing the 2024 edition of the European Researchers' Night (ERN) and its associated Build-up events, which fostered meaningful connections between researchers and the community. Co-designed with researchers, these events were implemented nationwide to ensure wide public participation, particularly targeting communities that typically have limited engagement with science communication such as .

Progress report by task

Task 2.1. – The theme of EU-EMBRACES NIGHT:

Across the nine venues, the public of the ERN had the opportunity to meet and interact with scientists from a variety of research fields, who shared their knowledge and the results of their investigations. Many activities centered on the EU Missions—Climate Change Adaptation, Cancer, Ocean and Waters, Climate-Neutral Cities, and Soil Deal for Europe. Other activities explored a broader range of scientific topics, highlighting the societal value of research.

Task 2.2. – Locations:

Events (Build-up activities and main NIGHTS) took place in streets, squares, public markets, beaches, theaters, monasteries, research centers, museums,

and many other public venues across the country (including Alviela, Braga, Bragança, Vila Nova de Foz Côa, Estremoz, Porto, Lagos, Lisboa, and Oeiras), bringing science directly to the public, including underserved groups, through partnerships with municipalities. The Build-up events engaged over 280 researchers and attracted approximately 27,500 participants across 32 sessions. These events featured workshops, field trips, BioBlitz activities, science cafés, talks, interactive exhibitions, renewable energy simulations, and hands-on activities. Topics covered a wide range of subjects, including regenerative agriculture, cancer awareness, renewable energy, climate change adaptation, geology, archaeology, robotics, and more.

Task 2.3 - NIGHT Activities:

The main NIGHT events involved approximately 5,000 participants and more than 500 scientists across nine cities and villages in Portugal. Over 230 activities were delivered, encompassing hands-on activities, workshops, exhibitions, science shows, demonstrations, competitions, games, escape rooms, speed dating with researchers, and astronomy observations. There were also virtual guided tours, stand-up comedy, music and dance showcases, tastings, and street art, providing very diverse and engaging experiences for attendees. EU Corners in each venue showcased EU-funded research and opportunities. Particular effort was made to engage communities that typically have limited access to science communication, including musicians and dancers from underserved neighborhoods, the Deaf community, individuals facing social and economic vulnerabilities such as deprivation, exclusion, and risk, as well as young students from vocational high schools specializing in communication. Events ran from 4:00 p.m. to midnight on September 27, 2024, with strong researcher-public interaction.

Task 2.4 - Mobilization of Researchers:

Around 780 researchers (between the build-up events and the main NIGHT event) were involved nationwide.

A detailed description of the build-up events and activities performed during the Night was reported in the deliverable D2.1 – Report on the activities during the NIGHT 2024, delivered in December 2024.

Work Package 3 (WP3): Researchers at Schools activities 1

WP3, which is still ongoing, has established connections between the research community, schools, and disadvantaged neighborhoods, fostering collaboration,

promoting STEM education, and addressing social inclusion. Activities have engaged students, underserved communities, and families through existing networks, including Ciência Viva Science Clubs, involving a total of 1,756 participants across Portugal.

A detailed description of the Researchers at Schools activities carried out was reported in the deliverable D3.1 - Report on the researchers at Schools' activities, delivered in January 2025.

Progress report by task

Task 3.1 - Meet the scientist campaign:

A total of 57 sessions (35 of which were in-person) were conducted, engaging 3,088 students aged 6 to 18 and involving 51 scientists. The sessions focused on EU Missions and beyond, aiming to promote STEM careers and inspire students and their families to participate in the upcoming ERN events.

Task 3.2. - Participatory debates:

In 2024, we organized 1 participatory debate with 22 students aged 12 to 17 and 2 scientists, enhancing their debate skills and raising awareness about EU Missions.

Task 3.3. - Program for Social Inclusion through Science and Technology:

In 2024, we organized 12 activities in disadvantaged neighborhoods, engaging 146 participants and 14 scientists, with the aim of democratizing access to scientific knowledge and fostering active citizenship.

Task 3.4 - Youth Ambassadors Program:

For the first edition of the NIGHT, we engaged 154 students from 9 different Clubes Ciência Viva in schools as collaborators during the event. These clubs are spaces for engagement with science and technology, created through partnerships between research centers and schools, with the aim to provide access to scientific practices and foster experimental learning. The participating students showcased their own research in their own stand during the first edition of the NIGHT at Marina de Oeiras, in collaboration with researchers from ITQB NOVA, contributing actively to the event's success.

Work Package 4 (WP4): Impact assessment 1

WP4 focused on evaluating the impact of pre-events, Researchers at Schools activities, and the European Researchers' Nights 2024 edition. A unified assessment

strategy was developed and implemented locally by partners using diverse tools while ensuring ethical practices, privacy, and data protection. Results were analyzed to measure progress toward the project's objectives and improve outreach efforts.

Progress report by task

Task 4.1. - Design of the Assessment Strategy:

A comprehensive assessment strategy was created, defining Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) aligned with six objectives: 1) raising awareness of science, 2) reaching underserved audiences, 3) promoting public engagement, 4) involving scientists, 5) showcasing EU-funded projects, and 6) organizing quality activities. The tools used included surveys (both paper-based and online), voting walls, show-of-hands voting, short reports, testimonies, and photographs.

Task 4.2. - Implementation of the Assessment Strategy

A decentralized approach was adopted for data collection across various locations. A document outlining the evaluation guidelines was created, and training was provided to the consortium partners and associated partners. Standardized templates were utilized, complemented by regular feedback sessions to ensure consistency while allowing for local adaptations.

Task 4.3. - Analysis of Results

Quantitative and qualitative data relative to all the activities held until December 2024 were analyzed using statistical and thematic methods. Findings helped evaluate the project's impact, inform future improvements, and are summarized in the deliverable D4.2 - Impact assessment delivered in January 2025 and shared publicly.

Also, the Deliverable D4.1 - Feedback to the EU Survey on the results of the European Researchers Night and on the Researchers at Schools Activities was delivered in October 2024.

Work Package 5 (WP5): Management 1

This work package focused on ensuring the successful implementation of EU-EMBRACES activities, effective internal and external communication, and compliance with EU requirements. ITQB NOVA coordinated the project, monitored progress, and handled administrative and financial management tasks.

Progress report by task

Task 5.1. – Internal Communication Flows:

Regular online meetings, held at least once a month and more frequently as needed, ensured synchronization among partners. Communication was facilitated through emails, Zoom calls, a dedicated WhatsApp group, and a shared drive for collaborative document editing. A kick-off meeting and ongoing video conferences supported effective collaboration.

The table below shows a list of the online meetings held.

Table 1 – Monthly online meetings of the consortium.

Meeting	Date	Agenda topics
Kick off meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	29/05/2024	Project launch, objectives, and coordination.
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	13/06/2024	General updates and discussion of next steps. Communication strategy, ERN.
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	22/07/2024	Feedback on deliverable <i>D1.1 Integrated communication plan</i> .
Website meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S)	17/07/2024	Website development and content review, coordination.
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	08/08/2024	Ongoing project updates and coordination.
Impact assessment training (Ciência Viva and associated partners, i3S, ITQB)	11/09/2024	Online training and guidance for teams across the 9 venues. Presentation and discussion of assessment guidelines and tools.

ERN preparation meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	18/09/2024	Status update, strategy discussions, and coordination for ERNs.
ERN debriefing (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	11/10/2024	Feedback on ERN events from September 2024. Status update on impact assessment and Researchers at Schools activities.
Year 1 Wrap-up Meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	25/10/2024	Feedback on the deliverable <i>D4.1 Feedback to the Eu survey on the results of the ERN and Researchers at Schools activities.</i> Update on <i>Meet the Scientist</i> program.
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	25/11/2024	Feedback on the deliverable <i>D1.2 Awareness campaign report for 2024.</i> Update on Participatory debates..
Project meeting (Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	16/12/2024	Feedback on the deliverable <i>D2.1 Report on the activities during the Night 2024.</i>
(Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	09/01/2025	Update Social inclusion through science and technology program, young ambassadors program point of situation.
(Ciência Viva, i3S, ITQB)	27/01/2025	Feedback on the deliverables <i>D3.1 Report on the researchers at Schools activities, D4.2 Report on impact assessment</i>

		2024, D5.1 Management report 2024.
--	--	------------------------------------

Task 5.2. – Internal Project Structure and Decision-Making:

ITQB NOVA oversaw progress monitoring, quality control, and budget compliance, as well as coordinated communication, assessment strategies, and dissemination plans. Work Package leaders were responsible for implementing tasks and reporting to the coordinator. Local venues, managed autonomously by Ciência Viva, enriched project quality through partnerships and alignment with project objectives. Decision-making was consensus-based, always reaching full agreement among all partners.

Task 5.3. – Communication with the European Commission:

ITQB NOVA ensured communication with the European Commission through regular deliverables, reports, and updates as needed.

This approach ensured the efficient management of activities, alignment with objectives, and collaboration among all partners and stakeholders.

3.2. Deviations from the plan, challenges and mitigation measures

Below follows a list of key challenges that we faced during the first 9 months of the project, for each WP, and mitigation strategies employed to address these challenges.

WP1: Awareness Campaign 1

Overall, the plan and goals for WP1 were met, even if some communication and dissemination actions were deferred for implementation in WP6. Some issues were detected on the website, which are currently being addressed. The intended improvements will result in a reformulation of the website for the remainder of the project. Many of these issues were identified prior to the ERN 2024 main event. However, due to the short timeframe and intense workload, along with the necessity of maintaining an accessible website during this critical period of the project, we opted to gather insights and feedback during the event and then address these challenges. This year, we will focus on making the necessary changes and adaptations to improve user experience by the 2025 edition. This reformulation will be carried out in close collaboration between the communication team (i3S) and the

hosting website team (Ciência Viva).

As for social media management and content creation to feed it, further collaboration must be fostered in this second leg of the project to ensure that all venues are properly featured and their activities promoted. To that end, it is crucial, however, that all of them engage more with the main event's account and provide the required material for the communication team to produce content that highlights the whole spectrum of activities and approaches EU-EMBRACES comprehends.

WP2: Activities during the Night 1

The overall plan and goals for this work package were successfully met. Specifically, for the build-up activities, instead of the 27 initially planned for the first year, we successfully carried out 54 activities, exceeding expectations. As for the main NIGHT 1 events, everything proceeded as planned, without any significant deviations.

WP3: Researchers at Schools activities 1

We foresee that all planned events will be completed by the end of the project as originally envisioned. However, it is important to highlight that due to the academic calendar, school-based activities (such as the *Meet the Scientists* program and the Participatory Debates) only began in September 2024. Consequently, the distribution of activities throughout the project's duration will be more concentrated during this school year (2024/2025).

On the other hand, for the *Youth Ambassadors* program, although the plan was to establish partnerships with Ciência Viva clubs during this academic year to enable student involvement in the second edition of ERN, an already well-established relationship—particularly between ITQB and some Ciência Viva clubs—allowed us to involve a number of students in the first edition that was nearly four times the originally planned figure.

WP4: Impact assessment 1

There have been no significant changes to the planned methodologies and tools for impact evaluation. We have been able to implement the processes as planned. However, a general challenge in impact assessment lies in standardizing data collection, especially considering the diversity of partners and their respective resources.

One area we aim to improve, though it is a known challenge, is increasing the response rate from researchers, particularly in events involving large numbers of

researchers participating simultaneously (such as some Build-up events and the ERNs). One strategy we are considering is collecting data during the event itself to ensure higher participation in the surveys.

Despite these challenges, we have managed to cover data for the vast majority of events conducted so far. Finally, for some of the more recent events, we are still awaiting data from the organizing partners, which is not surprising given the usual delay between the event's occurrence and the receipt of the corresponding data.

WP5: Management I

Overall, the management activities under WP5 have proceeded as planned, with no significant deviations or issues encountered. The established timelines, procedures, and coordination mechanisms have been successfully followed, ensuring smooth communication and collaboration among partners. No particular challenges have arisen, and the project management has remained effective in supporting the achievement of the project's goals.

4. | Current impact overview

Table 2 - Impact overview of EU-EMBRACES at month 9

Foreseen Impact (project as a whole)	State of the art at M9	Additional information (if applicable)
Short-term result		
A set of activities and events involving researchers and lay-audiences, in particular young people, and underserved audiences;	32 build-up events; 9 ERN events; 57 meet the scientists events; 1 participatory debate; 12 Social inclusion through science and technology events; 43 actions specifically with young people;	This count includes 4 activities during the ERN of Oeiras aimed at

	19 actions specifically with underserved audiences;	underserved audiences.
A Youth Ambassadors network;	154 students engaged to lead and animate activities during the NIGHT;	These students, along with others who will participate in the next edition of the ERN, will receive training in science communication through specialized workshops.
Many citizens across the country participating in science outreach activities;	Over 35,755 people have participated in EU-Embraces science outreach events by the end of 2024;	Includes build-up events, the main NIGHT events, Meet the scientists campaign, Participatory debates, Social inclusion through science and technology, and Youth Ambassadors program.
Researchers from all scientific areas engaged in science outreach activities;	<p>835 researchers involved so far from research areas that includes:</p> <p>Natural sciences: 47%</p> <p>Medical and Health Sciences: 17%</p> <p>Agricultural Sciences: 12%</p> <p>Engineering and Technology: 10%</p> <p>Social Sciences: 4%</p> <p>Exact Sciences: 3%</p> <p>Humanities: 2%</p> <p>Environmental Sciences: 1%</p> <p>Interdisciplinary: 1%</p> <p>Pharmaceutical Sciences: 1%</p> <p>Law: 1%</p> <p>Science Communication: 1%</p> <p>Marine Biotechnology: 1%</p> <p>Unknown: 2%</p>	

EU Missions highlighted;	EU missions presented in 66% of the activities;	
Research institutions with more visibility.	68 scientific institutions involved (institutional participation);	
Mid-term outcomes		
Increase the proportion of the national population engaging with science, particularly among underserved audiences such as ethnic minorities, migrants, and socio-economically disadvantaged populations. We anticipate that creating new opportunities for citizens to encounter science will spark greater interest in science-related issues in the future, leading to broader participation in science outreach activities and venues;	<p>Among the 1,569 surveys administered to participants of outreach events, 21% reported that this was their first time having direct contact with a scientist.</p> <p>Focusing exclusively on surveys from participants of the <i>Meet the Scientist</i> activities (out of 616 surveys), this percentage increases to 27%, with an additional 12% stating that they were unsure.</p>	
By involving school students in science, we expect to break barriers they may have in considering research as a potential career, showing that science is not too complicated nor uninteresting. We aim to bring a new cohort of students, specially from minorities and underserved groups, to universities, and later on to	3,410 students involved;	<p>This figure includes only the students who participated in the Researchers at Schools activities by the end of 2024—including the Meet the Scientists campaign, participatory debates, and youth ambassadors.</p> <p>To this number, students who</p>

scientific and academic careers.		participated in the build-up events and NEI should be added, for which only estimates are available: 760 and 800, respectively.
By involving researchers in different types of science outreach initiatives, we contribute to improving their communication skills and giving them new perspectives on the public's concerns and opinions on their scientific topic.	<p>Number of researchers involved in outreach initiatives: 835</p> <p>11% of researchers known to have participated in outreach activities for the first time</p>	
Research centres and universities realise the importance of participating in science outreach activities that go beyond preaching to the choir and start considering new strategies for reaching underserved audiences.	68 scientific institutions involved (institutional participation);	A number of institutions proactively reached out to the organizing partners to express their interest in participating in the ERN

5. | Plans for upcoming months (10–20)

In accordance with the Gantt chart, the upcoming months will focus on concluding the activities already planned within the framework of the WPs and tasks scheduled to end by Month 12 (April 2025). Following this, attention will shift to implementing the WPs planned for the period M13–M20. Specifically:

- **WP3/WP8:** Completion of the remaining *Researchers at Schools* activities (e.g., *Meet the Scientists* campaign, Participatory Debates, Program for Social

Inclusion through Science and Technology, and Youth Ambassadors Program), many of which are already scheduled .

- **WP4:** Analysis of impact data from the remaining WP3 activities, conducted between January and April 2025.
- **WP5/WP10:** Ongoing management, coordination, and monitoring of progress, alongside administrative and financial handling of both the ongoing WPs and those scheduled for M13-M20.
- **WP6:** Development and execution of the awareness campaign related to the 2025 edition of the ERN as part of the year-round concept.
- **WP7:** Implementation of build-up activities and the ERNs 2025.
- **WP9:** Implementation of the impact assessment activities for the period M13-M18 and analysis of the results.

5.1 | Risk Management for upcoming months

No new risks have been identified beyond those already outlined in the Grant Agreement.

6. | Conclusion

As the EU-EMBRACES project progresses through its initial phase (M1–M12, May 2024 to April 2025), the consortium has successfully achieved the key management and support objectives set for this period. Each partner has carried out their assigned tasks, ensuring that activities were implemented effectively and according to plan. Work Packages 1 (Awareness Campaign 1) and 2 (Activities during the Night 1) have been successfully completed, while Work Packages 3 (Researchers at Schools 1), 4 (Impact Assessment 1), and 5 (Management 1) are ongoing and advancing as scheduled, with no significant deviations or disruptions.

The consortium has demonstrated strong collaboration, leveraging its collective expertise to foster engagement and inclusivity in science communication. A core focus of the project has been addressing socio-economic disparities in access to science and innovation. By actively involving underrepresented communities—particularly those from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds—the project has illustrated how Horizon Europe Missions can positively impact lives.

The impact of the project in its first nine months has been substantial, with tangible results reflecting the consortium's commitment to its mission. Key achievements include:

- **32 build-up events** to create momentum and awareness;
- **9 European Researchers' Night (ERN) events**, engaging broad audiences;
- **57 Meet the Scientists events**, strengthening direct interactions between researchers and the public;
- **1 participatory debate**, promoting dialogue on critical scientific issues in students;
- **12 social inclusion through science and technology events**, ensuring outreach to underrepresented communities.

These efforts have resulted in impressive engagement metrics:

- **34,101 participants** actively involved in the project's activities;
- **839 researchers** participating in the initiatives;
- Media coverage across **37+ major channels**, including television and online publications;
- A strong digital presence, with **32,000 social media users** and **8,300 website visitors**.

As the project moves into its next phase (M10–M20), the consortium remains committed to sustaining this momentum. With a well-coordinated team and a shared vision, EU-EMBRACES is on track to achieve its overarching goal of empowering minds and fostering a more inclusive and accessible scientific landscape across Europe.